

MULTI-SEMIOTIC FEATURES OF FILM DISCOURSE

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Abstract: Cinematography is one of the most influential means of mass communication. This unique cultural phenomenon is characterised by rapid development, global distribution and impact on the audience worldwide. Being a complex multi-semiotic formation, film discourse consists of systems of signs that form a certain hierarchy. In this article, multi-semiotic nature of film discourse will be analyzed and clarified with bright examples.

Key words: multi-semiotic nature, semiosphere, synergetic feature, film semiotics, sign system, index, film frame, Cinematographic code, onomatopoeia, protagonist.

Film discourse is a symbol system that seems to arise from the interplay between different discourses in the semiosphere and texts in the discourse sphere. It refers to the analysis, discussion, and interpretation of films as a form of communication and art. In other words, it can represent the things that are illustrated in the literary discourse by showing another linguistic layer in a different way. It involves examining how films convey meaning, emotions, and messages through visual, audio, and narrative elements. Film discourse is a vivid example of synthesis of different types of signs in a common semantic, functional and structural sphere. The combination of simple signs produces complex signs of the first order which, in turn, form even more complicated signs of the second order (Mechkovskaya, 2017). Film discourse encompasses a wide range of approaches, including formal analysis of film techniques, critical analysis of themes and representations, and cultural analysis of how films reflect and shape societal norms and values. Semiotics is the study of signs and symbols and how they are used to convey meaning. When applied to film discourse, semiotics looks at how the visual, auditory, and narrative elements of a film work together to create meaning for the viewer. Here are some key concepts in the semiotics of film discourse.

In film, signs and symbols are used to communicate meaning to the audience. Signs can be anything that stands for or represents something else, such as an object, gesture, color, or sound. Symbols are signs that have a specific

cultural or conventional meaning. Semiotics examines how signs and symbols in film are arranged and combined to create layers of meaning for the viewer.

Iconicity refers to the resemblance between a sign and what it represents. For example, a close-up of a character's face in distress is an iconic sign of sadness. Indexicality refers to signs that have a causal or correlational relationship with what they represent. For example, smoke is an indexical sign of fire. In film, these concepts are used to create visual and auditory cues that guide the viewer's interpretation of the narrative.

Film relies on various codes and conventions to convey meaning to the audience. These codes include visual codes (such as lighting, framing, and composition), auditory codes (such as sound effects and music), and narrative codes (such as editing, continuity, and genre conventions). Semiotics helps analyze how these codes are used in film to create specific meanings and evoke particular emotional responses.

Intertextuality refers to the ways in which texts refer to, quote, or mimic other texts. In film, intertextuality can involve references to other films, genres, or cultural texts. Semiotics helps analyze how these references shape the viewer's interpretation of the film and contribute to its overall meaning.

Polysemy is the idea that signs and symbols can have multiple, layered meanings. In film, different viewers may interpret the same sign or symbol in different ways based on their personal experiences, cultural background, and knowledge of film conventions. Semiotics helps uncover the diverse meanings that can be generated by a single image or scene in a film.

Multi-semiotic and synergetic features of film discourse are studied by film semiotics – an approach in which the film is viewed as a ‘specific sign system or set of sign systems.’ Film semiotics is based on structural linguistics, poetics, ethnology and is a consistent approach to the description of linguistic, visual and other means that affect the viewer’s perception of a film. Film discourse is an open, multi-semiotic system that is harder to characterize than any stable system, whose changes over an extended period of time are negligible. An endless supply of visuals, or iconic signs, that may be combined in numerous ways with other signals to convey the open-ended character of film discourse. According to Mitry (2000), images do not always have explicit meanings, and their role is not limited to expressing one and the same meaning every time. In addition, the openness of film discourse is connected with its multimedia character (which allows the viewer to individually determine the strategy of perception) and with the operation of many codes (only partially the

same for the author and the viewer or for different viewers), which eventually leads to a variability of understanding of a film and the emergence of new meanings, associations and symbols. Film discourse is characterised by sign heterogeneity which, according to many researchers, was inherent even in the earliest silent films where captions and an oral narrative by special commentators were used (Mechkovskaya, 2017). Furthermore, silent movies communicated through the motions and facial expressions of its protagonists; all that may be naturally articulated through words could be conveyed without the need for spoken conversation. The film changed over time such that the conversations coincided with the other sign systems; initially, the dialogues did not blend in with the music and moving image. Subsequently, linguistic ways of expression started to take center stage, and both the visual and verbal aspects gained equal weight.

Signs of film discourse are divided into linguistic and non-linguistic. In each group, according to Pierce's classification, icons, indexes and symbols are distinguished. Language means are mainly represented by signs and symbols that are either written (captions and inscriptions that are part of the film's reality – a poster, a street name, a letter) and oral (voiced speech of actors, off-screen text, a song) (Slyshkin & Efremova, 2004). Indexes and iconic signs are few in a language; both types, however, are used in film discourse – intonation, interjections and shifters are all examples of indexes in a natural language while onomatopoeia is iconic (Mechkovskaya, 2017). The non-linguistic component of film discourse is to a large extent represented by iconic and index signs which can be both visual and audial. The audial part (natural noises, technical noise and music), as well as episodes of documentary films inside a feature film, are index signs. The visual part (the images of people, animals and objects that perform sequences of movements, gestures, facial expressions) consists mainly of iconic and index signs (Slyshkin & Efremova, 2004). In the process of film perception, the information transmitted by different semiotic systems is being decoded and the meaning becomes clear. In her study, Donskaya (2007) identifies fourteen semiotic systems which compound to the multi-semiotic structure of media discourse. Three of them are linguistic: oral speech, written text and letter tactics; the others are non-linguistic: colour, film frame division, dance, kinesics, statics, facial expression, music, singing, sound effects, costume, appearance and the state of characters / phenomena / objects. Each semiotic system operates its own signs and rules of their combination – codes. There are also codes that work between semiotic systems to join them to express a

particular meaning. Due to multiple codes interacting in film discourse, signs of different levels acquire special connections, develop a special connotative and / or symbolic meaning. Film discourse may acquire unexpected implicit meaning, which is not received directly, but by building close and distant logical and semantic links, often going beyond the boundaries of film discourse in the semiosphere of culture (Zaichenko, 2017). The code is the key with which the viewer can understand where exactly he should be looking for the meaning of an image or which links are essential at some point. Cinematographic codes include editing, angle, framing, light, plot and artistic space and some others (Slyshkin & Efremova, 2004).

This article therefore illustrates that film discourse has a number of semiotic features which make it different from many other kinds of discourse. The semiotics of film discourse provides a framework for understanding how signs and symbols are used to create meaning in film, and how viewers interpret and decode these meanings based on their cultural, social, and individual contexts. By analyzing the visual, auditory, and narrative elements of a film through a semiotic lens, we can gain deeper insight into how films communicate ideas, emotions, and messages to their audiences.

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